

Chemistry of Heterocycles. Part-II. 6π Electrocyclisation of Aza-1,3,5-hexatrienes and 1,3,5,7-Octatetraenes to Pyridines

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4-Benzalamino-3-methyl-5-styrylisoxazoles (4) have been thermally cyclised to 3-methyl-5,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydroisoxazolo[4,5-b]pyridines (6). The vinylogue of 4, *viz.* 3-methyl-4-cinnamylideneamino-5-styrylisoxazole (7) has also given the pyridine (9) instead of the expected azocine (8). The isoxazole Schiff bases have been obtained from the aminoisoxazole (3) by condensation with aromatic aldehydes. Ir, pmr and mass spectra have been discussed in support of the structures.

SYNTHESIS of pyridines by the electrocyclic ring-closure of azahexatrienes amounting to isomerisation are not known. The only known reactions related to this area are the electrocyclic ring-closures attended with eliminations, reviewed by Jutz¹ and transformations of these trienes into five-membered rings, surveyed by George *et al.*² We have very recently reported in a preliminary communication³, a thermal electrocyclic reaction on isoxazole Schiff bases, strictly an isomerisation. In this paper, we report the full details of the investigation. This method, by the way, is also an elegant one-step general synthesis of isoxazolo[4,5-b]pyridines which hitherto required a multistep synthetic sequence⁴⁻⁷.

under reflux for 3 h. Removal of the solvent followed by crystallisation furnished tlc-pure products, characterised as 3-methyl-5,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydroisoxazolo[4,5-b]pyridines (6) (Table 1) rather than the expected 3-methyl-5,6-diaryl-5,6-dihydroisoxazolo[4,5-b]pyridines (5). In the latter the isoxazole ring is not aromatic but has *ortho*-quinonoid structure and hence, it might be isomerising to 6 which is more stable. In undergoing this *in situ* isomerisation the first formed product 5 is exhibiting a [1,5]-sigmatropic rearrangement⁸. The 1,2-dihydropyridine structure assigned to the product is supported from ir (3400-3300 cm^{-1}) and ¹H nmr (a broad one-proton peak in the down field disappearing on

The starting materials for the synthetic sequence, *viz.* 3-methyl-4-benzalamino-5-styrylisoxazoles (6) have been obtained from 3,5-dimethyl-4-nitroisoxazole⁹ (1) which on regioselective condensation with various aromatic aldehydes gave the 3-methyl-4-nitro-5-styrylisoxazoles (2). The nitroisoxazoles have been converted into the Schiff bases by reduction of the nitro group and the subsequent condensation of the amine (3) with benzaldehydes. Electrocyclic ring-closure has been effected by heating the diphenyl ether solution of benzalaminoisoxazoles

shaking with D₂O) spectra which point to the presence of NH. The 1,4-dihydropyridine structure for the product is ruled out as the ¹H nmr spectrum does not show a methylene. With a view to extend the reaction to aza-1,3,5,7-octatetraenes, the vinylogue of 6, namely 3-methyl-4-cinnamylideneamino-5-styrylisoxazole (7) was subjected to thermal cyclisation in diphenyl ether to get the azocine (8). Instead of the expected 8, the product was again the pyridine (9). The ir and ¹H nmr spectral data confirm the presence of NH. The ¹H nmr spectrum

displayed a doublet of doublet at 7.1 (J 15 Hz) which is diagnostic of a *trans*-1,2-disubstituted ethylene, thus strongly supporting the structure 9. The reason as to why 7 is behaving like a hexatriene rather than an octatetraene is not clear. But Huisgen *et al.*¹⁰ obtained cyclooctatrienes only by the electrocyclic ring-closure of 2,4,6,8-decatetraenes. The compounds prepared along with the properties are given in Table I.

TABLE I—DATA OF ISOXAZOLO[4,5-*b*]PYRIDINES (6)*

Sl. no.	Ar	Ar'	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	Phenyl	**Phenyl	212 ^a	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O
2.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	198 ^b	35	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂
3.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	284 ^b	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂
4.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	254 ^b	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ OBr
5.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino-phenyl	240 ^b	45	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₃ O
6.	Phenyl	3,4-Methylenedioxy-phenyl	214 ^b	35	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂
7.	Phenyl	α -Thienyl	193 ^c	25	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS
8.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	155 ^b	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ OCl
9.	Phenyl	2,4-Dichlorophenyl	190 ^b	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ OCl ₂
10.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	230 ^b	25	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂
11.	Phenyl	<i>m</i> -Methoxy- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	235 ^b	45	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃
12.	Phenyl	Styryl	194 ^c	20	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₂ O

* Consistent C, H, N analyses observed.

** Compound reported, Ref. 3.

Solvent of crystallisation: a=benzene; b=benzene-ethylacetate, c=petroleum ether-benzene.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra were run in KBr matrix on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The 90 MHz ¹H nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard and the mass spectra on a Hitachi RMU-6E instrument at 70 eV.

4-Benzalamino-3-methyl-5-styrylisoxazoles (4).

General procedure: 4-Amino-3-methyl-5-styrylisoxazole (0.01 mol) and aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) were refluxed in methanol for 0.5-2 h. The solution on concentration followed by cooling gave the products which were recrystallised from suitable solvent.

3-Methyl-5,6-diaryl-4,5-dihydroisoxazolo[4,5-*b*]pyridines (6). **General procedure:** A solution of 3-methyl-4-benzalamino-5-styrylisoxazole¹¹ (4; 1 g)

in diphenyl ether (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated product filtered and washed with petroleum ether to remove trace of diphenyl ether. Crystallisation from suitable solvent gave isoxazolopyridine as pale yellow crystals, $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3400–3350 cm⁻¹ (NH); ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.9–8.0 (12H, m, ArH+C–H+C=CHPh) and 12.0 (1H, br, NH); m/z 288 (100%), 211 (30%), 185 (20%) and 104 (22%).

3-Methyl-5-styryl-6-phenyl-4,5-dihydroisoxazolo[4,5-*b*]pyridine (9): 3-Methyl-4-cinnamylideneamino-5-styrylisoxazole (7; 1 g) was refluxed in diphenyl ether (15 ml) for 3 h, cooled and the solid filtered. It was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to give the cyclised product 9, $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3370–3300 (NH), 970 cm⁻¹ (*trans* CH=CH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1 (2H, dd, J 15 Hz, CH=CH), 7.0–8.1 (12H, m, ArH+C–H+C=CHPh) and 9.5 (1H, br, NH); m/z 314 (100%), 313 (79%), 297 (12%), 286 (13%), 285 (36%), 237 (22%), 184 (19%), 183 (24%), 157 (15%) and 130 (26%).

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References

1. J. O. JUTZ, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1978, 73, 125.
2. M. V. GEORGE, A. MITRA and K. R. SUKUMARAN, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1980, 19, 973.
3. S. SAILAJA, C. J. RAO, E. RAJA NARENDAR and A. K. MURTHY, *Synthesis*, 1983, 10, 839.
4. O. SKOETSCH, I. KOHLMAYER and E. BRECHTMAIER, *Synthesis*, 1979, 6, 449.
5. J. J. TUFARIELLO and S. A. ALI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1978, 47, 4647.
6. K. ARIMURA and S. MURAKAMI, Japan Pat., 1927663/1977.
7. G. ADEMBRI, A. CAMPARINI, F. PONTICELLI and P. TEDESCHI, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1975, 2190.
8. G. T. MORGAN and H. B. BURGESS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 699.
9. R. B. WOODWARD and R. HOFFMANN, "The Conservation of Orbital Symmetry", Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1971, p. 117.
10. R. HUISGEN, A. DAHMEN and H. HUBER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 89, 7130.
11. A. K. MURTHY, K. S. R. K. M. RAO and N. V. S. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1047.